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PENETRATION TESTING AND DEFENSE STRATEGIES

Mr. Ajas K S¹, Mr. Fares Rahman², Mr. Joel Deleep³, Mr. Joemon Johnson⁴, Ms. Shejina N M K A⁵

^{1,2,3,4} UG Students, Department of Computer Science and Engineering,

⁶ Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science and Engineering,
IES College of Engineering, Chittilappilly, Thrissur.

Abstract:

Objective- Penetration testing helps to secure networks, and highlights the security issues. In this paper investigate different aspects of penetration testing including tools, attack methodologies, and defense strategies. More specifically, we performed different penetration tests using a private networks, devices, and virtualized systems and tools. We predominately used tools within the Kali Linux suite. The attacks we performed included: Smartphone penetration testing, hacking phones Bluetooth, traffic sniffing, hacking WPA Protected Wi-Fi, Man-in-the-Middle attack, spying (accessing a PC microphone), hacking phones Bluetooth, and hacking remote PC via IP and open ports using advanced port scanner. The results are then summarized and discussed. The paper also outlined the detailed steps and methods while conducting these attacks.

Design/Methodology/Approach- There are many different tools that can be used for penetration testing. Several are available on the market that one can download and use for free. Many of them are even able to be customized; known as Open Source tools [2]. For example, the testing tool Kali Linux has its own built-in penetration tools; however, you can download and install additional tools to it. Most of these programs are being developed for Linux, with only a handful are being developed for Windows or Mac

Findings- The strategies that exist include antivirus, network cloaking, updating to the new system and using wpa2 encryption.

Limitations- All the strategies are easily bypassed including the wpa2 passwords.

Practical Implications- The strategies that are developed are easy to implement without much effort.

Originality/Value- This paper deals with various attacks on network and system by conducting penetration testing and will help to find the various vulnerabilities to develop strategies that can prevent these attacks thus improving the security of the system.

Keywords- Wi-Fi attack, Smartphone Hacking, Bluesnarfing, Packet Analyzer, Penetration Testing

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

Penetration testing is a simulation of an attack to verify the security of a system or environment to be analyzed. This test can be performed through physical means utilizing hardware, or through social engineering. The objective of this test is to examine, under extreme circumstances, the behavior of systems, networks, or personnel devices, in order to identify their weaknesses and vulnerabilities. In terms of tools, there exist penetration testing tools which simply analyze a system, as well as ones which actually attack the system to find vulnerabilities.

The purpose of this paper is to explain the use of and share some concepts for better understanding penetration testing. In our explanation of penetration testing we use the most common, simple and general concepts to make it clear and easy for readers with different background to use and understand the tools. In particular, this paper presents different penetration tests using a private networks, devices, and virtualized systems and tools. We predominately used tools within the Kali Linux suite. The attacks we performed included: Smartphone penetration testing, hacking phones Bluetooth, traffic sniffing, hacking WPA Protected Wi-Fi, The results are then summarized and discussed

The way the internet is used has created a suitable environment for the attackers to exploit easily. Android platform is widely used platform and attackers are using it to exploit the users and gain access to the phone. After gaining they can steal data access camera and much more. Users who are not aware of installing third party apps outside the store are the victims of such attacks. Usage of antivirus application is the old method to defend those attacks and hackers are able to bypass those entire antiviruses checking with the help of crypters, packers and binders. Install verified application provided in official app store. This will ensure the security of the applications installed. Avoid installing third party apps outside the store.

The same scenario is in the case of Wi-Fi networks, with this paper we are doing two different attacks on wireless networks including packet sniffing and WPA password cracking. On a first look WPA cracking only provide access to the internet service or data sharing, but rather than that an attacker has got wide range of opportunities to exploits the network and steals confidential data without much effort. The strategy which was developed is to use higher versions of encryption which is WPA2 with a combination of special characters, numbers or long non dictionary phrases.

Bluesnarfing is a Bluetooth intrusion technique that allows connecting to a Bluetooth device and gaining access to sms, call and contacts. When it comes to bluesnarfing the level or threat is low when compare to other attacks since this is only possible when the device is having its Bluetooth turned on. The best method to defend the attack is to turn off Bluetooth since attack is only possible when the Bluetooth is turned on.

For the development of protocols, it is essential to have a good and powerful protocol analyzer at hand. For networking protocols based on IP, which are used over Ethernet, there are numerous tools to switch the Ethernet card into promiscuous mode and subsequently sniff and analyze all packets that come along. Though the Wireshark was developed with a good intention it is widely used to analyze the packets over a network and someone who is good with TCP protocols can easily manipulate the packets and perform high level attack.

A simple approach to solve anonymous authentication problems is simply to combine both cryptographic primitives and anonymous communication protocols as follows. Let a user compute an anonymously-authenticated token (e.g., group signature), and send it to a server via an anonymous channel (e.g., using Tor). Then, the server can directly authenticate the user without compromising anonymity. However, another problem arises here: how to establish a secure channel (i.e., flowed data is encrypted). If the server utilizes a user public key (certified by a trusted Certificate Authority (CA) in a Public Key Infrastructure (PKI)), it can identify the user because a certificate contains information on the key holder. The same problem arises even if symmetric key encryption is used. Assume that the server attempts to exchange a secret key with an end user. Because the server does not know the actual end user, it does not know its user public key for executing a key exchange protocol. Therefore, though both anonymity and end-to-end encryption are recognized as important properties in privacy preserving communication, the current PKI contradicts anonymity, and it is highly desirable to construct a secure and anonymous communication protocol that achieves anonymity and end-to-end encryption simultaneously.

II. RELATED WORKS

2.1 Penetration Testing for Android Smartphones

Android is a mobile operating system developed by Google, based on the Linux kernel and designed primarily for touch screen mobile device such as smart phones and tablets. Android's user interface is mainly based on direct manipulation, using touch gestures that loosely correspond to real-world actions, such as swiping, tapping and pinching, to manipulate on-screen objects, along with a virtual keyboard for text input. In addition to touch screen devices, Google has further developed Android TV for televisions, Android Auto for cars and Android Wear for wrist watches, each with a specialized user interface. Variants of Android are also used on notebooks, game consoles, digital cameras, and other electronics.

In the proposed mechanism an android application is created in for testing the security of the android system. Application program is created with a view to simplify discovery and information gathering stage.

Information Gathering is the very first step a hacker follows. Indeed, during this critical phase, the auditor collects as much data as possible about the target. It enables to validate or reject hypothesis, map the target network and have a precise idea of the infrastructure to better target the tests of next phases. Issues concerned about the android system, the android architecture are validated and studied thoroughly and penetration was carried out using the Kali Linux.

2.2 Bluetooth Intrusion Techniques

Bluetooth technology has grown through the years, but because of the increase, security has become an issue. In the entire world the people interacting and use this technology, when transferring data through devices or when using the computer or personal devices, null confidentiality and null authenticity are factors to remain secure. How this technology are very common, malicious exploits attack all time searching find access. In this paper we have shown different exploits and vulnerabilities that are either in the design already, or have been maliciously exploited.

Some of these exploits are Bluesnarfing, Bluejacking, Bluebugging, etc. By understanding these exploits, one can gain a general idea of how vulnerable Bluetooth possibly could be.

Bluebug is the name of a Bluetooth security loophole that has been identified by Adam Laurie from A.L. Digital Ltd. on some Blue-tooth-enabled cell phones. Exploiting this loophole allows the unauthorized downloading phone books and call lists, the sending and reading of SMS messages, connection to the INTERNET, changing a service provider, initiating a call through the phone, and many more. Under ideal conditions, it is possible for a Bluebug attack to only take a few seconds. Due to the limited transmit power of class 2 Bluetooth radios; the distance of the victim's device to the attacker's device during the attack should not exceed 10-15 meters. A directional antenna can be attached to the radio in order to increase the range. Since the Bluebug security loophole allows to issue AT (modem) commands via a covert channel to the vulnerable phones without prompting the owner of the phone, this security flaw does allow a vast number of things that may be done when the phone is attacked via Bluetooth

Bluejacking is a trivial exploit that utilizes a design flaw in the OBEX layer. Any random person can easily Spam another person's mobile phone by sending a text message. The original designs intentions were for a person to easily send another person their business card via their mobile phone. However, that technology has been exploited by people now sending random messages to another person when the device is close enough to detect the other Bluetooth device.

Bluesmack is a DOS (Denial of Service) attack. This attack exploits the L2CAP layer, which is responsible for echo requests similar to ICMP (Internet Control Message Protocol) ping. Bluesmack sends an enormous amount of ping requests to another device, which makes the victim's device unresponsive to any services. This attack is similar to "Ping of Death" and "Smurf Attack". Since a standard Bluetooth device cannot handle large amounts of ping requests, this will result in a buffer overflow and cause the device to be unavailable. This method can be tweaked to create a buffer overflow by injecting malicious code into the device.

2.3 Packet Analysis with Wireshark and off-the-shelf hardware

The ability to overhear and analyze packets is essential for the development of protocols for IEEE 802.15.4-based Wireless Sensor Networks. Besides a number of commercial hardware and software offers, only very few projects put effort in developing such solutions.

In this paper practical approach to sniffing radio packet switch off-the-shelf hardware. By using the Contiki Operating System on a standard T-Mote Sky radio packets can be overheard and then transported to a standard Linux PC that is connected to the USB port. On the PC, the overheard packets are fed into Wireshark for further protocol analysis. Custom dissectors in Wireshark allow the intuitive and efficient analysis of protocol message and thereby the diagnosis of potential problems

Wireshark is very similar to tcpdump, but has a graphical front-end, plus some integrated sorting and filtering options. Wireshark lets the user put network interface controllers that support promiscuous mode into that mode, so they can see all traffic visible on that interface, not just traffic addressed to one of the interface's configured addresses and broadcast/multicast traffic. However, when capturing with a packet analyzer in promiscuous mode on a port on a network switch, not all traffic through the switch is necessarily sent to the port where the capture is done, so capturing in promiscuous mode is not necessarily sufficient to see all network traffic. Port mirroring or

various network taps extend capture to any point on the network. Simple passive taps are extremely resistant to tampering. On GNU/Linux, BSD, and macOS, with libpcap 1.0.0 or later, Wireshark 1.4 and later can also put wireless network interface controllers into monitor mode.

If a remote machine captures packets and sends the captured packets to a machine running Wireshark using the TZSP protocol or the protocol used by OmniPeek, Wireshark dissects those packets, so it can analyze packets captured on a remote machine at the time that they are captured.

2.4 Advanced Attack Against Wireless Networks Wep, Wpa/Wpa2-Personal And Wpa/Wpa2Enterprise

Hackers who will seek for data to steal or compromise functionality. While the traditional security measures are less efficient the wireless attack surface presents a singular and difficult challenge. Most of the wireless nets are much unprotected so it is vulnerable to assault. When we consider Wi-Fi most of the people have consciousness about two major encryption techniques (WEP) Wired Equivalency Protocol and (WPA) Wi-Fi Protected Access which were frequently employed. WPA is modern and securing when compared to WEP.

In the proposed system the first step is configuring the interface to scan the networks near the attacker. The cracking is completed under a handshake which is captured. The attack can be implemented at enterprise level also.

Even though WPA was developed with high complexity, it holds its own flaws that are starting to take advantage, attacking the authentication that gives direct access to the wireless web. When attacking WPAPSK authentication, the attacker can also hold the power to decrypt traffic since the PMK is recovered. Encryption attacks are just emerging against WPA networks. These approaches provide the power to decrypt traffic but do not permit the attacker to fully join the mesh as a lawful user.

Wi-Fi Protected Access (WPA) and Wi-Fi Protected Access II (WPA2) are two security protocols and security certification programs developed by the Wi-Fi Alliance to secure wireless computer networks. The Alliance defined these in response to serious weaknesses researchers had found in the previous system, Wired Equivalent Privacy (WEP). WPA (sometimes referred to as the draft IEEE 802.11i standard) became available in 2003. The Wi-Fi Alliance intended it as an intermediate measure in anticipation of the availability of the more secure and complex WPA2. WPA2 became available in 2004 and is common shorthand for the full IEEE 802.11i (or IEEE 802.11i-2004) standard. A flaw in a feature added to Wi-Fi, called Wi-Fi Protected Setup, allows WPA and WPA2 security to be bypassed and effectively broken in many situations.^[2] WPA and WPA2 security implemented without using the Wi-Fi Protected Setup feature are unaffected by the security vulnerability.

The attack is done in done in 4 phases as follows

- Configuring
- Passive Scanning
- Active Scanning
- Packet Death
- Cracking

1. Configuration

Interface is configured for beginning the attack. At this phase an interface is set for monitoring all wireless networks near the attacker's computer system.

2. Passive Scanning

The nearby networks are monitored and scanned at this phase. Details such as MAC address, channel, SSID can be analyzed.

3. Active Scanning

A network suitable for WPA attack is chose from the active scanning module. After locking to that particular network, attacker has to wait for a new user to join.

4. Packet Deauth

A certain number of deauth packets are sent to deauthenticate the device with the network. A handshake process will be implemented and a captured file will be created.

5. Cracking

The captured file is cracked using aricrack-ng suite. For this process a wordlist or a dictionary is used and a bruteforce attack is done.

III. STRATEGY ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING STRATEGIES

Using Antivirus applications to scan the system and remove malicious applications. Updating system with all the patches that is available removing all the existing vulnerabilities. Securing with WPA2 password making the password difficult to crack. Network cloaking to maintain the confidentiality of the network.

3.1.1 DRAWBACKS

- Advanced malicious applications will be created using crypters, binders or packers allowing to bypass the Antivirus application.
- Though the system is updated, we can never assure 100% security to any system.
- WPA2 passwords alone can't fix the problem, since there are tools to crack WPA2 ordinary passwords.
- Hidden networks can be easily be traced using tools and cloaking the network compromises the privacy of the network.

3.2 PROPOSED STRATEGIES

This paper proposes a list of strategies to secure the network and system to prevent nay types of attacks after conduction pen-testing. The proposed strategies ensure improved security of the system and network. We can never create system that guarantees 100% security, the best way is to improve the security by introducing security measures. The paper deals with four types of attack scenarios. The way a system interacts with the outer world has become wider and these has created a space for the attackers to gaining access and steal relevant information. Information security has now become a important topic that even top level enterprises analyze, to create a better cyber space it is also relevant to act very carefully. The attacks that are performed include android platform and wireless network.

Android is a mobile operating system, based on the Linux kernel and designed primarily for touch screen mobile devices such as Smartphone and tablets. Android's user interface is mainly based on direct manipulation, using touch gestures that loosely correspond to real-world actions, such as swiping, tapping and pinching, to manipulate on-screen objects, along with a virtual keyboard for text input. Android applications are software applications running on the android platform. There are a lot of pirated applications circulated over the internet and users are not aware about the malicious purpose of those applications. With this paper we are performing an android attack on a Smartphone running android os 4.4 kitkat. The attack can gain full access to the Smartphone with the help of an application. The best way to prevent is to install applications only from the playstore. Though installing an anti virus can detect and prevent malicious applications, usage of advanced crypters and binders can bypass antivirus detection and can perform malicious activities. The convenient way is to not to install apps outside the official playstore. If user is still in need of the app it should be verified before installing and turn on the app verification in settings. Verifying app will send information regarding the application to Google and will warn you when an app is determined to be malicious even if it passes muster the first time around.

Bluetooth technology has grown through the years, but because of the increase, security has become an issue. In the entire world the people interacting and use this technology, when transferring data through devices or when using the computer or personal devices, null confidentiality and null authenticity are factors to remain secure. How this technology are very common, malicious exploits attack all time searching find access. In this paper we have shown different exploits and vulnerabilities that are either in the design already, or have been maliciously exploited. Some of these exploits are Bluesnarfing, Bluejacking, Bluebugging, etc. By understanding these exploits, one can gain a general idea of how vulnerable Bluetooth possibly could be.

One of the most effective methods to protect your phone (or table) from attackers to gain access through Bluetooth is to simply turn off Bluetooth on these devices. Most people do not use any Bluetooth related features in their devices and would not lose any functionality having Bluetooth perpetually off. For people who do often use Bluetooth on their devices, we would suggest that they only turn on the Bluetooth when needed. Doing so needlessly exposes them to Bluetooth threats and attacks like the one we performed and described.

For the development of protocols, it is essential to have a good and powerful protocol analyzer at hand. For networking protocols based on IP, which are used over Ethernet, there are numerous tools to switch the Ethernet card into promiscuous mode and subsequently sniff and analyse all packets that come along. Wireshark is a network protocol analyzer. It lets you capture and interactively browse the traffic running on a computer network. It has a rich and powerful feature set and is world's most popular tool of its kind. It runs on most computing platforms including Windows, OS X, Linux, and UNIX.

There is no effective method to completely prevent attackers from sniffing your network. But consistent analysis of the packets send can determine whether any ARP spoofing is done. Also ensure that the HSTS enabled browsers are used. HSTS is HTTP Strict Transport Security which is a web security policy which protect websites form protocol downgrade attacks and cookie hijacking. HSTS enables browsers such as Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox

will prevent from traffic sniffing. Though the attacker will be able to sniff the traffic attacker won't be able to extract valuable credentials though any downgrade attacks are performed. Also use HTTPS enabled sites while accessing internet over a public Wi-Fi since HTTP sites are vulnerable to session hijacking attack.

When we consider Wi-Fi most of the people have consciousness about two major encryption techniques (WEP) Wired Equivalency Protocol and (WPA) Wi-Fi Protected Access which were frequently employed. WPA is modern and securing when compared to WEP. Though WPA is modern WPA passwords are attacked and can be cracked easily when any dictionary word or passphrase are used. The next advanced level of WPA2 is also vulnerable to cracking using the Aircrack suite .But a strong password with combination of special characters; number will ensure the security of the access point. MAC id filtering along with Wireless Intrusion Detections systems will allow detecting any unwanted attacks in the network. Though the attack is based on the password to access the wireless network an attacker is capable of performing advanced attacks.

3.2.1 ADVANTAGES OF STRATEGIES

Install verified applications.

Install verified application provided in official app store. This will ensure the security of the applications installed. Avoid installing third party apps outside the store. The authentic applications will be safe when compared to the third party applications. The publisher of the application is known and if any malicious activity is performed it is easy to take action against the publisher and remove it from the playstore. If user is still in need of the app it should be verified before installing and turn on the app verification in settings. Verifying app will send information regarding the application to Google and will warn you when an app is determined to be malicious even if it passes muster the first time around.

Turn off Bluetooth when not in use.

Turn off the Bluetooth when not in use is the best practical strategy to defend the attack. The reason that makes this the best strategy the attacks are only possible when the Bluetooth is turned on in the device. Most people does not use the Bluetooth and its feature and is exposed to these attacks unknowingly.

Consistent Analysis.

The network should be analyzed consistently to check whether any unwanted packet injections are done , or any man in the middle attack is been carried out this will ensure packet spoofing attacks such as ARP spoofing .

Use HTTPS

This strategy is well effective if a traffic sniffing is being carried out by the attacker. The traffic sniffing is mainly done based on Public wifi in malls, railways stations and other public places. The usage of HTTPS sites will ensure the security since HTTPS is encrypted with TLS and SSL. HTTPS provides authentication of the website and associated web server with which one is communicating, which protects against man-in-the-middle attacks. Additionally, it provides bidirectional encryption of communications between a client and server, which protects against eavesdropping and tampering with or forging the contents of the communication.

Strong Passwords

Use higher versions of encryption which is WPA2 with a combination of special characters, numbers or long non dictionary phrases. WPA is next version of WPA with better encryption. Still it is vulnerable to cracking. The efficient way to prevent attacks against wifi passwords is to use strong passwords with a combination of number and special characters. The password cracking is mainly implemented using bruteforce attack which is performed based on a dictionary or wordlist. Non dictionary words will prevent the password from bruteforce attack. Combination and phrases make it difficult to crack as the attack work like a trial and error technique.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this project we performed various attacks that can be performed or being performed by attackers to gain access to the systems and steal data .Greater level of security can minimize data theft. While connecting to a network validate the security. Security is has become a challenging field with the growth of internet. Penetration tools are getting produced without any limitations. No system can assure you full 100 percent security. The more strategies developed the more it will be difficult to attack. With the internet growing daily cyber attacks are also increasing and it is time to think about effective strategies to prevent any data loss.

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